

MACHINABILITY STUDIES OF METAL ADDITIVE MANUFACTURED EOS MARAGING STEEL USING ELECTROCHEMICAL MACHINE

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ABSTRACT: For electrochemical machining (ECM) machinability investigations, metal additive produced EOS maraging steel is taken into consideration. Die casting, tooling, and the aviation sectors all employ this substance. Voltage, electrolyte concentration, duty cycle, and the use of an L16 orthogonal array (OA) employing four levels were among the ECM process factors taken into consideration for optimization in this work. For performance analysis, a multi-criteria decision-making technique called entropy-based multi-objective optimization on the basis of ratio analysis (MOORA) is utilized. A 60% duty cycle, electrolyte concentrations of 45 gms/l, and 14 volts are suggested for the best machining results, according to the study. Based on the mean effect table, the ideal configuration is 14 volts, 40 gms/l of electrolyte concentration, and 60% duty cycle. According to the results of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), voltage is responsible for about 59.49% of the machining performance. About 7.62% of machining performance is attributed to electrolyte concentration and 12.13% to duty cycle. Every micro machined hole was scanned using a scanning electron microscope (SEM), and the machined hole quality was assessed by taking various resolution photographs.

KEYWORDS: MOORA, Entropy method, Duty cycle, electrolyte concentration, ANOVA, EOS maraging steel

1 INTRODUCTION

Metal additive manufacturing (AM) is increasingly being used to make prototypes, especially with materials like Maraging steel. This technology enables the creation of complex geometries and optimised designs that standard manufacturing methods may fail to achieve. However, in order to achieve the requisite mechanical qualities and surface polish, post-processing machining is frequently required. Prototypes made from Maraging steel by AM are frequently employed in the aerospace, automotive, and tooling industries, where high performance and precision are required. Oliveira, Jardini, and Del Conte (2020) investigate the effect of different cutting parameters on surface roughness and residual

stress in maraging steel specimens manufactured using AM. The authors conducted experiments to determine how different machining variables, such as cutting speed and feed rate, affect the mechanical properties of the material. Surface roughness was strongly influenced by cutting speed and feed rate. Cutting speeds (over 200 m/min) and feed rates (less than 0.1 mm/tooth) resulted in much smoother surfaces. An ideal combination of faster cutting speed and lower feed rate resulted in the highest surface quality with the least amount of roughness. Tascioglu et al. (2021) studied the effect of ageing and finish machining on the surface integrity of maraging steel manufactured by selective laser melting. After ageing, the pieces underwent finish machining procedures, such as turning with a lathe, to achieve the desired surface polish. Finish

machining after ageing reduced surface roughness substantially, increasing the specimens' overall surface quality. Ciric-Kostic et al. (2017) investigate the impact of machining and heat treatment on the fatigue parameters of maraging steel manufactured using Direct Metal Laser Sintering (DMLS). The data show that both machining and heat treatment have a considerable impact on the steel's fatigue life. Machining generally increases surface polish, which improves fatigue performance, but heat treatment changes the microstructure, increasing strength and fatigue resistance. Sarafan et al. (2021) investigate the characteristics of maraging steel made using a hybrid additive/subtractive manufacturing process. The study discovered that subtractive machining improved dimensional accuracy and surface polish, while maraging steel maintained its excellent hardness and strength attributes after post-processing. Godara et al. (2024) evaluate the effect of build orientations on the micro-drilling performance of Selective Laser Melted (SLM)-fabricated Maraging steel (18-Ni-300). The experimental method used SLM to fabricate Maraging steel specimens in various construction orientations (vertical, horizontal, and inclined). These samples were then subjected to micro-drilling experiments to determine drilling forces, surface quality, and material removal rates. The study found that build direction has a substantial impact on microdrilling performance. Vertically manufactured samples had a superior surface polish and lower drilling forces than horizontal and inclined specimens. Narayanan et al. (2020) investigated the use of large pulsed electron beam (LPEB) irradiation to improve the surface attributes of SLM maraging steel. The experimental procedure comprised using SLM to create maraging steel samples and treating them with LPEB. The influence of electron-beam irradiation on surface roughness, microstructure, and mechanical characteristics (hardness and wear resistance) was investigated. LPEB irradiation considerably improved the surface characteristics of maraging steel. Surface roughness was reduced, while the microstructure was improved, resulting in greater hardness and wear resistance. Ituarte et al. (2020) examine the surface modification of additively made 18% nickel maraging steel using ultrasonic vibration-assisted ball burnishing. The results demonstrated that ultrasonic vibration-assisted ball burnishing greatly improved the surface finish of maraging steel, resulting in lower surface roughness and increased surface hardness. Vandzura et al. (2023) investigate the impact of abrasive water jet cutting on the surface quality of MS1 material (a type of maraging steel) produced using the DMLS technology. Several parameters, including jet

pressure, abrasive substance, and cutting speed, were varied to determine their impact on surface finish and quality. The study found that abrasive water jet cutting significantly reduced the surface roughness of the DMLS-prepared MS1 material. Croccolo et al. (2019) evaluate the effects of machining, heat treatment, and surface treatment on as-built maraging steel treated using DMLS. The experimental approach entailed employing DMLS to create Maraging steel specimens, which were then subjected to a variety of post-processing procedures such as machining, heat, and surface treatments. Machining improved the surface finish, whereas heat treatment affected the microstructure, increasing hardness and tensile strength. Olmi et al. (2018) conducted fatigue testing on the samples and investigated the influence of machining allowances on fatigue performance. They reported that machining allowances improved surface quality, which improved fatigue performance even more.

To summarize, metal AM has proven to be a flexible technology, particularly for creating complex prototypes using materials such as maraging steel. While AM allows for the fabrication of complicated geometries, optimized topologies, and parts with moderate density, post-processing is required to provide the requisite mechanical characteristics and surface finishes. Cutting, final machining, micro-drilling, and advanced treatments such as large pulsed electron beam (LPEB) irradiation and ultrasonic vibration-assisted ball burnishing have all been shown to improve surface quality and mechanical performance. Machining operations, particularly when combined with heat treatment, considerably increase fatigue life, surface roughness, and material strength. Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that using a combination of additive and subtractive manufacturing processes improves dimensional accuracy while maintaining maraging steel's natural hardness and strength. However, as these studies show the relevance of machining in producing high-performance components; electrochemical machining (ECM) appears as a promising, non-traditional method for surface enhancement. ECM, a contactless process that removes material through controlled anodic dissolution, has benefits such as the elimination of mechanical tensions and heat-affected zones, making it perfect for refining the surfaces of complicated AM-produced maraging steel components. ECM is ideal for hard-to-machine materials such as maraging steel because it allows precise control over material removal, resulting in clean surfaces with minimum wear or fatigue effects. Thus, combining electrochemical machining with metal AM could improve the quality of maraging steel prototypes,

making them more trustworthy for applications in industries like aerospace, automotive, and tooling that require high precision and exceptional surface integrity. The voltage, electrolyte concentration, duty cycle, and the selection of an L₁₆ orthogonal array (OA) were considered utilising four steps of selection. Performance analysis is carried out utilising the multi-criteria decision machining approach, also known as entropy-based multi-objective optimisation on the basis of ratio analysis (MOORA). Chakraborty et al. (2023) examined the usefulness of the MOORA method for factor optimisation, whereas Das et al. (2013) used MOORA to investigate technical institution performance. According to the archived literature, ECM process optimisation utilising entropy and MOORA is scant, thus ECM parameters are optimised using the former method in this study.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The chemical composition of EOS Maraging Steel parts follows US classifications of 18% Ni Maraging 300, European 1.2709, and German X3NiCoMoTi 18-9-5. This steel has outstanding mechanical qualities and may be heat-treated with a simple thermal age-hardening procedure to achieve high strength and hardness levels. EOS Maraging Steel parts are easily machinable and can be age-hardened to above 50 HRC at 490 °C (914 °F) for 6 hours. Parts can be machined, spark-eroded, welded, shot-peened, polished, and coated in both as-built and age-hardened states. Heat treatment can minimize or eliminate anisotropy in parts built layer wise [13]. EOS maraging steel finds application in Injection molding tools & inserts and mechanical engineering parts. The Energy Dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy (EDAX) tests were performed to check the composition of the specimen EOS Maraging Steel and it revealed that all the alloying materials were present in the expected composition. Figures 1 and 2 shows the elements chart and machined EOS Maraging Steel respectively. This component was subjected to ECM machinability studies for making micro holes. Figure 3 show the setup used for making micro-holes on the EOS Maraging Steel. The ECM setup consist of machine structure, machining tank, filter with circulation pump, tool feeders with stepper motor and pulsed power supply. In ECM the tool electrode is the stitching needle of diameter 460µm is connected with negative power supply and workpiece EOS Maraging Steel is connected with positive power supply. The machining method makes use of a NaNO₃ electrolyte. The electrolyte is used for bridging the two electrodes, and the pulse power supply commences and sustains the

electrochemical machining process according to Faraday's law of electrolysis [14-16].

Fig 1. EDAX of EOS Maraging Steel

Fig 2. ECMed EOS maraging steel specimen

In this experiment, the ECM process variables voltage, electrolyte concentration, and duty cycle are changed based on material removal rate (MRR) and overcut. The studies described in table 1 are carried out using L₁₆ OA. MRR is computed by dividing the workpiece thickness by the machining time. The specimen's thickness is 2mm, and the machining time is measured in minutes. The overcut is defined as the millimeter difference between the diameter of the tool electrode and the machined hole [17].

Table 1.L16 OA Design of experiments

Exp t.	Voltage (V)	Electrolyte concentration(gms/l)	Duty cycle in (%)	MRR in mm/min	OC in mm
1	10	30	50	0.048	0.522
2	10	35	60	0.070	0.281
3	10	40	70	0.072	0.328
4	10	45	80	0.086	0.350
5	12	30	60	0.063	0.519
6	12	35	50	0.047	0.574

7	12	40	80	0.088	0.390
8	12	45	70	0.079	0.395
9	14	30	70	0.102	0.340
10	14	35	80	0.115	0.350
11	14	40	50	0.066	0.215
12	14	45	60	0.078	0.415
13	16	30	80	0.094	0.853
14	16	35	70	0.110	0.673
15	16	40	60	0.123	0.643
16	16	45	50	0.133	0.400

Fig 3.ECM and subsystems

3 ENTROPY METHOD

The Entropy technique is the most effective strategy to determine the significance of responses. To compute the weight of responses, follow the methods outlined below. The equation α_{ij} represents the performance of the i^{th} alternative on the j^{th} attribute, where m is the number of alternatives and n is the number of attributes (Gadakh et al., 2013).

$$\delta = \begin{bmatrix} \delta_{11} & \delta_{12} & \delta_{13} & \dots & \dots & \delta_{1n} \\ \delta_{21} & \delta_{22} & \delta_{23} & \dots & \dots & \delta_{2n} \\ \delta_{31} & \delta_{32} & \delta_{33} & \dots & \dots & \delta_{3n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \delta_{m1} & \delta_{m2} & \delta_{m3} & \dots & \dots & \delta_{mn} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

To normalize responses the following equation is used.

$$\theta_{ij} = \frac{\delta_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m \delta_{ij}^2}} \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (2)$$

θ_{ij} is a value with no dimension which range between the interval $[0, 1]$ for the i^{th} alternative and j^{th} attribute, which designate the normalized performance.

The entropy value En_j is calculated using equation 3.

$$En_j = -a \sum_{i=1}^m \theta_{ij} \ln(\theta_{ij}) \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (3)$$

Where $a = 1/\ln m$ is constant, m is the no of alternatives.

The degree of divergence is calculated using equation 4

$$DD_j = 1 - n_j \quad (4)$$

Equation 5 could be considered to calculate the weight of the j^{th} criterion.

$$wt_j = \frac{\alpha_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n \alpha_j} \quad (5)$$

3.1 MOORA (Multi-objective optimization on the basis of ratio analysis)

The goal of multi-objective optimization, sometimes referred to as multi-criteria or multi-attribute optimization is to maximize many conflicting objectives within the limitations that are imposed. Developed by Brauers and Zavadskas in 2006, the MOORA (Multi-Objective Optimization by Ratio Analysis) method is a useful tool for resolving difficult decision-making issues, especially in the manufacturing industry. The MOORA method is distinguished from other multi-criteria decision-making techniques by its simplicity and ease of application. Because the approach is based on simple ratio analysis, it requires few mathematical calculations, which makes it especially useful for decision-makers who lack a solid foundation in mathematics. The MOORA approach also provides faster computational processing times. Its accessibility is increased by the fact that, in contrast to many other multi-criteria decision-making procedures, it can be used with programs like Microsoft Excel.

The MOORA approach is renowned for remaining stable in a variety of settings involving decision-making. The method begins with a decision matrix that evaluates different options' performances according to a number of different criteria.

Next, a ratio system is built to evaluate the performance of each alternative by contrasting it with a denominator that indicates the total performance of all alternatives for a specific criterion. Brauers and Zavadskas (2006) looked at a number of ratio systems, such as the total ratio and Krth ratio, and found that the square root of the sum of squares of each alternative for each attribute is the

most useful denominator. This ratio is expressed as follows:

$$\check{\eta}_{ij} = \eta_{ij} / \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m \eta_{ij}^2} \quad (j = 1,2,3,\dots,n) \quad (6)$$

The dimensionless number $\check{\eta}_{ij}$ represents the normalized performance of the i-th alternative on the j-th attribute, with values ranging between 0 and 1. In multi-objective optimization, normalized performances are subtracted for non-useful attributes to minimize their influence and summed for positive attributes to maximize their impact.

Thus, the optimization issue becomes

$$x_i = \sum_{j=1}^k \check{\eta}_{ij} - \sum_{j=k+1}^n \check{\eta}_{ij} \quad (7)$$

In the equation, (k) represents the number of attributes to maximize, while (k and n) denotes the number of attributes to minimize. The term (x_i) represents the normalized evaluation value of the i-th alternative across all attributes. Prioritizing attributes can be done by multiplying them by their respective weight, or significance coefficient, since some attributes might be more significant than others [18]. When the attribute weights are considered, Eq. (3) becomes:

$$x_i = \sum_{j=1}^k w_{tj} \check{\eta}_{ij} - \sum_{j=g+1}^n w_{tj} \check{\eta}_{ij} \quad (j=1,2,\dots,n) \quad (8)$$

The weight of the j-th attribute w_{ij} can be determined using methods like the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) or the entropy approach. Depending on the mix of advantageous and non-beneficial traits, the x_i value in the choice matrix could be positive or negative. The optimal choice has the highest x_i value and the worst has the lowest, indicating the final preference represented by the ordinal ranking of x_i.

Material Removal Rate (MRR) and Overcut (OC) were optimized using the entropy-weighted MOORA (Multi-Objective Optimization on the Basis of Ratio Analysis) technique. The MOORA values and ranks were calculated using equations (1–8) and are shown in Table 2. By applying the entropy approach, the attribute weights were calculated, yielding (wt_j = 0.4593) for OC and (wt_j = 0.5407) for MRR. As the ideal combination for better machining performance, the option with the highest MOORA value is regarded as the best and comes in first place [20–22].

Thus, the greatest MOORA value (0.1612) was obtained by experimental run 12, which was followed by runs 15 (0.1612) and 11 (0.1590). It was discovered that 14 volts, 45 gms/l of electrolyte

concentration, and a 60% duty cycle were the ideal machining conditions for getting the best results.

Table 2.MOORA based Ranking

Expt	η_{ij}^2		$\check{\eta}_{ij}$		x_i	Ran
1	0.0023	0.2725	0.2404	0.1820	0.087	12
2	0.0049	0.0790	0.1778	0.2699	0.092	11
3	0.0053	0.1076	0.1324	0.2984	0.068	15
4	0.0075	0.1225	0.2470	0.2028	0.097	10
5	0.0041	0.2694	0.2217	0.2054	0.099	9
6	0.0023	0.3295	0.2851	0.1768	0.085	14
7	0.0079	0.1521	0.3224	0.1820	0.087	12
8	0.0064	0.1560	0.1844	0.1118	0.053	16
9	0.0105	0.1156	0.2192	0.2158	0.104	6
10	0.0134	0.1225	0.2637	0.4435	0.136	5
11	0.0044	0.0462	0.3071	0.3499	0.159	3
12	0.0062	0.1722	0.3427	0.3343	0.161	1
13	0.0090	0.7276	0.3705	0.2080	0.100	7
14	0.0122	0.4529	0.3071	0.3499	0.159	3
15	0.0152	0.4134	0.3427	0.3343	0.161	1
16	0.0177	0.1600	0.3705	0.2080	0.100	7
	$\sum_{i=1}^m \eta_{ij}^2$		4.3349	4.0727		
	En_j $= -a \sum_{i=1}^m \theta_{ij} \ln(\theta_{ij})$		2.1593 5	1.9424 3		
	$wt_j = \frac{\alpha_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n \alpha_j}$		0.5178	0.4822		

3.2 ANOVA table for MOORA

In order to determine important process parameters and how they affect machining performance, the MOORA values are statistically evaluated using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) [23]. Table 3 illustrates the results, which show that voltage contributes roughly 59.49% to the overall machining performance, duty cycle 12.13%, and electrolyte concentration 7.62%. The best set of parameters for machining performance is 14 volts, 40 gms/l electrolyte concentrations, and a 60% duty cycle, according to the mean effect analysis.

Table 3. ANOVA table for MOORA

Symbol	Degree of Freedom	Seq. SS	Adj. MS	F-value	% Contribution
Voltage	3	0.0040	0.001336	2.1343	59.49
Electrolyte concentration	3	0.0026	0.000862	1.377	7.62
Duty cycle	3	0.0045	0.001497	2.391	12.13
Error	6	0.0038	0.000626		20.76
Total	15	0.014843	0.00099		100

Table 4. Main effects table for MOORA

Machining factors	S/N ratio for MOORA				
	LEVEL 1	LEVEL 2	LEVEL 3	LEVEL 4	Delta
Voltage	0.0865	0.0815	0.1403*	0.1303	0.0588
Electrolyte concentration	0.0978	0.1183	0.1192*	0.1052	0.0214
Duty cycle	0.1081	0.1285*	0.0964	0.0654	0.0631

*optimal parametric combination by MOORA

Fig 4. Mean effect plot

Fig 5. Hole machine at 14V, Electrolyte Concentration 45gms/litres, Duty Cycle 60%

Fig 6. Hole machine at 14V, Electrolyte Concentration 40gms/litres, Duty Cycle 50%

Figure 4 illustrates how increasing the voltage range of 12 to 14V lowers the OC and increases the MRR. The ideal voltage level for cutting EOS maraging Steel is 14V. Because of a combination of ageing and martensitic transformation processes, the maraging steels are distinguished by their extremely high strength and toughness. A greater voltage is used for electrochemical dissolution since the 3D printed material has a density of 8.0g/cm³[13]. The electrolyte concentration exhibits increasing trends in the 30–40 gm/l concentration range and additional dips at higher concentrations. This is caused by a number of things, including debris buildup between electrodes and dissolved metals. Figure 5 clearly shows that more pores are depicted in the hole machined at 45 gms/l of electrolyte due to increased dissolution and stray current effect. The holes cut under ideal conditions are shown in Figures 6 and 7. Despite the holes' flawless round shape, there are a few delaminated patches and tiny pores visible around their periphery. The creation of these regions is attributed to the presence of silicon and oxide forms during electrochemical processes. Future studies can focus on use of solid electrolyte for this of 3D printed materials with ultra-high strength and toughness [24-25].

Fig 7. Voltage 16V, Electrolyte Concentration 40gms/l, Duty Cycle 60%

In case of duty cycle the ECM performance increase for the range of 50 to 60% and beyond there is declining trend noticed in the figure. At constant pulse frequency 50 to 60% of time is used for machining and remaining 50 to 40% is used to remove the debris after machining. Hence, 50 to 60% of duty cycle is the optimal level for attaining maximum MRR and lesser OC.

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

1. The material removal rate (MRR) and overcut are used in this experiment to adjust the ECM process variables of voltage, electrolyte concentration, and duty cycle. The L_{16} OA is the location of the experiments. Entropy-based Multi-objective optimisation on the basis of ratio analysis (MOORA), a multi-criteria decision making method, is used to perform performance analysis.
2. The entropy technique was utilised to apply weights to the attributes: ($w_{tj} = 0.5407$) for MRR and ($w_{tj} = 0.4593$) for OC. For best machining performance, the MOORA technique suggests 14 volts, 45 gms/l of electrolyte concentration, and a 60% duty cycle.
3. The mean effect table indicates that 14 volts, 40 gms/l of electrolyte concentration, and 60% duty cycle are the ideal combinations. According to the ANOVA result, voltage is responsible for about 59.49% of the performance during milling. The contribution of duty cycle and electrolyte content to machining performance is 12.13% and 7.62%, respectively.
4. Holes that are machined under ideal circumstances have a flawless round form, very few areas of delamination, and visible

micro-pores all around the circle of the hole. These regions occur because of the presence of silicon and oxide forms during the electrochemical reactions. Furthermore, the ideal level to achieve the highest MRR and the lowest OC is between 50 and 60% of the duty cycle.

5. Future studies can focus on use of solid electrolyte for this of 3 printed materials with ultra-high strength and toughness.

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